

QUIZ

LAST NAME: Kumar
FIRST NAME: Mukund
PROGRAM CODE: DSDD
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INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What are the key structural elements that need to be covered while writing an essay?**

- Introduction, Body, Conclusion.**¹
- Introduction, writing, evidence, publication.
- Drafting, writing, research, conclusion.
- Writing, editing, new draft, second stage of writing.

2. **What types of writing require a Style Guide?**

- Commercial or business writing, journalism, web copywriting, blog writing.
- Blog writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, sports column
- Commercial writing, journalism, web copywriting, blogs.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

Technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, web copywriting.²

3. **In research, what kind of questions researchers try to ask?**

Conceptual and analytical.

Practical and numerical.

Conceptual, practical and applied.³

Conceptual, practical, applied and numerical.

4. **Why warrants are difficult to identify for researchers new to the field of study?**

Advanced researchers rarely spell out their principles of reasoning because they know their colleagues take them for granted.

Warrants typically have exceptions that experts also take for granted and therefore rarely state, forcing new researchers to figure them out as well.

Experts also know when not to state an obvious warrant or its limitations.

All of the above.⁴

5. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, books by a single author are referenced with which of the following formula? (pay attention to the punctuation or lack thereof presented in each possible answer)**

² Ibid., 24.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

⁴ Ibid., 41.

- Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Date. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Edition (if existing). Date. Title (italics). Editor(s)/Translator(s) (if existing). Place: Publication Press.⁵**
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title (in quotation marks), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.

6. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, if a publication has several authors, how are they correctly referenced regarding their first and last names?**

- The names of all authors are inverted.
- None of the author's names are inverted.
- When there are more than six authors, one should only reference the first author and then use "et al."
- Only the first listed author's name is in inverted order; names of additional authors follow but are inverted.⁶**

7. **What are the key steps to follow while conducting a literature review in a qualitative dissertation?**

- Identify and retrieve literature, review and analyz, and write a review.
- Conceptual framework, Identify and retrieve literature, review and analyz, and write a review.
- Identify and retrieve literature, review and analyz, and conceptual framework.

⁵ Ibid., 136.

⁶ Ibid., 138.

Identify and retrieve literature, review and analyze, write a review and develop conceptual framework.⁷

8. **Why it is important to use interpretation outline tool in presenting conclusion of the research?**

- It makes researcher's job easy to follow a structure for conclusion.
- Allow to develop actionable recommendations.
- Stimulate critical thinking and reflection about the deeper meanings behind research findings.

All of the above.⁸

9. **How acronyms are required to be presented as per European Commission English Style Guide?**

Acronyms with five letters or less are uppercased.⁹

- Acronyms with six letters or more should be uppercased.
- Acronyms with six letters or more should not be written with an initial capital followed by lower case.
- All of the above.

10. **What is the governing articles (under the Treaty of functioning of the European Union) for the European Commission?**

Article 244 and 250.¹⁰

Article 244 and 252.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A roadmap from beginning to end*. (Sage Publications, 2008), 50- 59.

⁸ Ibid., 128-129.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. (European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 27.

¹⁰ Ibid., 62.

- Article 250 and 252.
- Article 244, 250 and 252.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.